

Modeling Spatially-Correlated Cellular Networks by Using Inhomogeneous Poisson Point Processes

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Abstract. In this paper, we introduce the Inhomogeneous Double Thinning (IDT) approach, which allows us to analyze the performance of downlink cellular networks in which the Base Stations (BSs) constitute a stationary Point Process (PP) that exhibits some degree of spatial repulsion (i.e., inhibition). The accuracy of the proposed IDT approach is substantiated by using empirical data for the spatial distribution of the BSs.

Keywords: Cellular Networks · Stochastic Geometry · Inhomogeneous Point Processes · Spatial Inhibition.

1 Introduction

Poisson Point Processes (PPPs) have been extensively used for modeling the locations of cellular Base Stations (BSs) [1]. Examples include Heterogeneous Cellular Networks (HCNs) [2], millimeter-wave cellular HCNs [3], Multiple-Input-Multiple-Output (MIMO) HCNs [4], and the energy efficiency of cellular networks [5]. General mathematical frameworks that account for the impact of antenna radiation patterns, spatial blockages, and the network load are available as well [6].

Using the PPPs has the inherent advantage of mathematical tractability. However, the locations of the Base Stations (BSs) are usually spatially correlated. Therefore, some authors have recently studied the performance of cellular networks by using other point processes, e.g., [7]- [9], where Determinantal Point Processes (DPP), Ginibre Point Processes (GPP), and Log-Gaussian Cox Processes (LGCP) are considered, respectively. The resulting analytical frameworks, however, are less tractable than the PPP.

Motivated by the considerations, we introduce a new approach for modeling and analyzing the performance of spatially-correlated cellular networks, which is based on Inhomogeneous PPPs (I-PPPs). The choice of using I-PPPs is motivated by their analytical tractability and by the fact that empirical evidence shows that spatial correlations may be difficult to disentangle from spatial inhomogeneities [10, Section 7.3.5.2]. It is worth noting that the spatial models

Table 1. Notation

Symbol/Function	Definition
$\mathbb{E}\{\cdot\}, \mathbb{1}(\cdot)$	Expectation operator, indicator function
$\mathbb{E}^{!x}\{\cdot\}$	Expectation (reduced Palm measure)
$f_X(\cdot)$	Probability density function (PDF) of X
$\mathcal{M}_{I,X}(\cdot)$	Laplace functional conditioned on X
${}_2F_1(\cdot, \cdot, \cdot, \cdot)$	Gauss hypergeometric function
$\max\{x, y\}, \min\{x, y\}$	Maximum and minimum of x and y
$(a_F, b_F, c_F), (a_K, b_K, c_K)$	Parameters of the approximating I-PPPs

in [7]- [9] are all based on stationary point processes. On the other hand, I-PPPs are non-stationary point processes, which implies that the performance of a randomly chosen user is no longer independent on its actual location. In our approach, we introduce an equivalent I-PPP whose inhomogeneity is created from the point of view of the typical user of the original motion-invariant point process. This makes our approach applicable for approximating several point processes. The proposed approach is referred to as Inhomogeneous Double Thinning (IDT) approach.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we present the system model. In Section 3, the IDT approach is introduced. In Section 4, the mathematical framework of the coverage probability is provided. In Section 5, the accuracy of the IDT approach is validated by using empirical data sets. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

Notation: The notation used in the paper can be found in Table 1.

2 System Model

The BSs are modeled as points of a stationary point process, Ψ_{BS} , of density λ_{BS} . The locations of the BSs are denoted by $x \in \Psi_{\text{BS}} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$. The Mobile Terminals (MTs) are distributed uniformly at random in \mathbb{R}^2 . A fully loaded network is considered. The serving BS is denoted by BS_0 , and its location is $x_0 \in \Psi_{\text{BS}}$. The interfering BSs constitute another point process, denoted by $\Psi_{\text{BS}}^{(1)}$. Each BS transmits with power P_{tx} . The power of the Gaussian noise is σ_{N}^2 .

For each BS-to-MT link, path-loss and fast-fading are considered. The path-loss is $l(x) = \kappa \|x\|^\gamma$, where κ and $\gamma > 2$ are the path-loss constant and the path-loss slope. The power gain, g_x , due to small-scale fading is an exponential random variable with unit mean.

The cell association criterion is based on the highest average received power. The location, x_0 , of the serving BS, BS_0 , is obtained as follows:

$$x_0 = \arg \max_{x \in \Psi_{\text{BS}}} \{1/l(x)\} = \arg \max_{x \in \Psi_{\text{BS}}} \{1/L_x\} \quad (1)$$

where $L_x = l(x)$ is a shorthand. As for the intended link, we have $L_0 = l(x_0) = \min_{x \in \Psi_{\text{BS}}} \{L_x\}$.

The coverage probability P_{cov} is defined as follows:

$$P_{\text{cov}} = \Pr \left\{ \frac{P_{\text{tx}} g_0 / L_0}{\sigma_N^2 + \sum_{x \in \Psi_{\text{BS}}^{(I)}} P_{\text{tx}} g_x / L_x} > T \right\} \quad (2)$$

where $\Psi_{\text{BS}}^{(I)} = \Psi_{\text{BS}} \setminus x_0$, and T is the decoding threshold.

Lemma 1. *The coverage probability in (2) can be expressed as follows:*

$$P_{\text{cov}} = \int_0^{+\infty} \exp(-\xi T \sigma_N^2 / P_{\text{tx}}) \mathcal{M}_{I, L_0}(\xi; T) f_{L_0}(\xi) d\xi \quad (3)$$

where $f_{L_0}(\cdot)$ is the probability density function of L_0 and $\mathcal{M}_{I, L_0}(\cdot; \cdot)$ is the Laplace functional of the point process, $\Psi_{\text{BS}}^{(I)} = \Psi_{\text{BS}} \setminus x_0$, of interfering BSs:

$$\mathcal{M}_{I, L_0}(\xi = L_0; T) = \mathbb{E}_{\Psi_{\text{BS}}^{I, x_0}} \left\{ \prod_{x \in \Psi_{\text{BS}}^{(I)}} (1 + T(\xi/l(x)))^{-1} \right\} \quad (4)$$

Proof. It directly follows from [1]. □

From (4) and (5), we conclude that to compute the coverage probability we need $f_{L_0}(\cdot)$, which depends on the Contact Distance Distribution (CDD) of the point process, and $\mathcal{M}_{I, L_0}(\cdot; \cdot)$, which depends on the reduced Palm distribution of the point process [12]. However, the CDD and reduced Palm distribution of a stationary point process may not be known or may not be mathematically tractable.

3 Inhomogeneous Double Thinning

The proposed approach for computing P_{cov} consists of introducing an equivalent system model based on I-PPPs. More precisely, the BSs are modeled as the superposition of the points of two *independent* isotropic I-PPPs, denoted by $\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}$ and $\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}$, with intensity measures $\Lambda_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}}(\cdot)$ and $\Lambda_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}}(\cdot)$, respectively. Since I-PPPs are not motion-invariant, we are interested in computing the coverage probability from the point of view of a *probe* MT located at the origin. The serving BS and interfering BSs are assumed to belong to $\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}$ and $\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}$, respectively, and are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} x_0^{(F)} &= \arg \max_{x \in \Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}} \{1/l(x)\} \\ \Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(I)} &= \Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(I)}(x_0^{(F)}) = \left\{ x \in \Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(K)} : l(x) > L_0^{(F)} = l(x_0^{(F)}) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

It is worth noting that the I-PPPs $\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}$ and $\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(I)}$ are only *conditionally independent*.

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{f}_{L_0^{(F)}}(\xi) &= \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa}\right)^{1/\gamma} \frac{1}{\gamma\xi} \Lambda_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}}^{(1)}\left(\mathcal{B}\left(0, \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa}\right)^{1/\gamma}\right)\right) \exp\left(-\Lambda_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}}\left(\mathcal{B}\left(0, \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa}\right)^{1/\gamma}\right)\right)\right) \\ \tilde{\mathcal{M}}_{1, L_0^{(F)}}(\xi; \mathbf{T}) &= \exp\left(-\int_{\xi}^{+\infty} \left(1 + \frac{z}{\mathbf{T}\xi}\right)^{-1} \left(\frac{z}{\kappa}\right)^{1/\gamma} \frac{1}{\gamma z} \Lambda_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}}^{(1)}\left(\mathcal{B}\left(0, \left(\frac{z}{\kappa}\right)^{1/\gamma}\right)\right) dz\right)\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

The coverage probability of the probe MT located at the origin can be formulated as follows:

$$\tilde{\text{P}}_{\text{cov}}^{(\mathbf{o})} = \Pr\left\{\frac{\text{P}_{\text{tx}}g_0/L_0^{(F)}}{\sigma_{\text{N}}^2 + \sum_{x \in \Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(1)}} \text{P}_{\text{tx}}g_x/l(x)} > \mathbf{T}\right\} \quad (6)$$

where the superscript (\mathbf{o}) denotes that (6) holds for the probe MT at the origin.

Lemma 2. *The coverage probability in (6) can be computed as follows:*

$$\tilde{\text{P}}_{\text{cov}}^{(\mathbf{o})} = \int_0^{+\infty} \exp(-\xi \mathbf{T} \sigma_{\text{N}}^2 / \text{P}_{\text{tx}}) \tilde{\mathcal{M}}_{1, L_0^{(F)}}(\xi; \mathbf{T}) \tilde{f}_{L_0^{(F)}}(\xi) d\xi \quad (7)$$

where $\tilde{f}_{L_0^{(F)}}(\cdot)$ is the probability density function of $L_0^{(F)}$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{M}}_{1, L_0^{(F)}}(\cdot; \cdot)$ is the Laplace functional of $\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(1)}$ given in (8) at the top of this page, and $\Lambda_{(\cdot)}^{(1)}(\mathcal{B}(0, r)) = d\Lambda_{(\cdot)}(\mathcal{B}(0, r))/dr$ is the first-order derivative of the intensity measure.

Proof. It follows from [6]. \square

In order to apply the IDT approach, the intensity measures $\Lambda_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}}(\cdot)$ and $\Lambda_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}}(\cdot)$ are determined with the objective of ensuring $\tilde{\text{P}}_{\text{cov}}^{(\mathbf{o})} \approx \text{P}_{\text{cov}}$. This is elaborated in the next section.

3.1 Intensity Measures of the I-PPPs

The intensity function of an I-PPP determines its intensity measure [11, Sec. 2.2]. Let $\lambda_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}(\cdot)$ and $\lambda_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}(\cdot)$ be the intensity functions of $\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}$ and $\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}$. The following holds:

$$\begin{aligned}\Lambda_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}}(\mathcal{B}(0, r)) &= 2\pi \int_0^r \lambda_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}(\zeta) \zeta d\zeta \\ \Lambda_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}}(\mathcal{B}(0, r)) &= 2\pi \int_0^r \lambda_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}(\zeta) \zeta d\zeta\end{aligned}\quad (9)$$

Let $(a_{\text{F}}, b_{\text{F}}, c_{\text{F}})$ and $(a_{\text{K}}, b_{\text{K}}, c_{\text{K}})$ be two triplets of non-negative real numbers, where $c_{\text{F}} \geq b_{\text{F}} \geq 1$ and $b_{\text{K}} \leq c_{\text{K}} \leq 1$. The following intensities are proposed to

model the spatial inhibition among the locations of the BSs:

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}(r) &= \lambda_{\text{BS}} c_{\text{F}} \min \{ (a_{\text{F}}/c_{\text{F}}) r + b_{\text{F}}/c_{\text{F}}, 1 \} \\ \lambda_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}(r) &= \lambda_{\text{BS}} \min \{ a_{\text{K}} r + b_{\text{K}}, c_{\text{K}} \}\end{aligned}\quad (10)$$

The intensity measures in (9) can be formulated as $\Lambda_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(\cdot)}}(\mathcal{B}(0, r)) = \Upsilon(r; a_{(\cdot)}, b_{(\cdot)}, c_{(\cdot)})$, where $\Upsilon(r; a, b, c)$ and its first-order derivative $\Upsilon^{(1)}(r; a, b, c)$ are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\Upsilon(r; a, b, c) &= 2\pi\lambda_{\text{BS}} \left((a/3)r^3 + (b/2)r^2 \right) \mathbb{1}(r \leq (c-b)/a) \\ &\quad + 2\pi\lambda_{\text{BS}} \left((c/2)r^2 - (c-b)^3/6a^2 \right) \mathbb{1}(r > (c-b)/a) \\ \Upsilon^{(1)}(r; a, b, c) &= 2\pi\lambda_{\text{BS}} (ar^2 + br) \mathbb{1}(r \leq (c-b)/a) \\ &\quad + 2\pi\lambda_{\text{BS}} cr \mathbb{1}(r > (c-b)/a)\end{aligned}\quad (11)$$

We propose to compute the triplets of parameters that determine the intensity measures $\Lambda_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}}(\cdot)$ by solving the following minimization problem:

$$(a_{\text{F}}, b_{\text{F}}, c_{\text{F}}) = \arg \min_{(a, b, c) \in \Omega_{\text{F}}} \left\{ \left| F_{\Psi_{\text{BS}}}(r) - F_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}}(r; a, b, c) \right|^2 \right\} \quad (12)$$

where $F_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}}(r; a, b, c)$ is the CDD of $\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}$ and $\Omega_{\text{F}} = \{(a_{\text{F}}, b_{\text{F}}, c_{\text{F}}) : c_{\text{F}} \geq b_{\text{F}} \geq 1\}$. $\Lambda_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}}(\cdot)$ can be obtained in the similar way, but by approximating the so-called “non-regularized” Ripley’s K-function of the point process [13].

4 Coverage Probability By Using the IDT Approach

The following theorem provides a tractable expression of $\tilde{\text{P}}_{\text{cov}}^{(\circ)}$ in (6). Two case studies are considered: i) the network is infinitely large and ii) the network has a finite size of radius R_{A} .

Theorem 1. $\tilde{\text{P}}_{\text{cov}}^{(\circ)}$ in (6) can be formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\text{P}}_{\text{cov}}^{(\circ)} &= \int_0^{\kappa(d_{\text{F}})^{\gamma}} \exp(-\xi T \sigma_{\text{N}}^2 / P_{\text{tx}}) \exp(-\mathcal{I}(\xi)) \mathcal{U}_{\text{IN}}(\xi) d\xi \\ &\quad + \int_{\kappa(d_{\text{F}})^{\gamma}}^{\Theta} \exp(-\xi T \sigma_{\text{N}}^2 / P_{\text{tx}}) \exp(-\mathcal{I}(\xi)) \mathcal{U}_{\text{OUT}}(\xi) d\xi\end{aligned}\quad (13)$$

where $d_{\text{F}} = \frac{c_{\text{F}} - b_{\text{F}}}{a_{\text{F}}}$, $d_{\text{K}} = \frac{c_{\text{K}} - b_{\text{K}}}{a_{\text{K}}}$, $\Theta \rightarrow \infty$ and $\mathcal{I}(\xi) = \mathcal{I}_{\infty}(\xi)$ for network with infinite size, $\Theta \rightarrow \kappa R_{\text{A}}^{\gamma}$ and $\mathcal{I}(\xi) = \mathcal{I}_{R_{\text{A}}}(\xi)$ for network with finite size, and $\mathcal{I}_{\infty}(\cdot)$, $\mathcal{I}_{R_{\text{A}}}(\cdot)$, $\mathcal{U}_{\text{IN}}(\cdot)$, $\mathcal{U}_{\text{OUT}}(\cdot)$ are defined in (14).

Proof. The proof is omitted due to space limitations. \square

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{U}_{\text{IN}}(\xi) &= 2\pi\lambda_{\text{BS}} \left(\frac{a_{\text{F}}}{\gamma\xi} \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa}\right)^{3/\gamma} + \frac{b_{\text{F}}}{\gamma\xi} \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa}\right)^{2/\gamma} \right) \exp \left(-2\pi\lambda_{\text{BS}} \left(\frac{a_{\text{F}}}{3} \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa}\right)^{3/\gamma} + \frac{b_{\text{F}}}{2} \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa}\right)^{2/\gamma} \right) \right) \\
\mathcal{U}_{\text{OUT}}(\xi) &= 2\pi\lambda_{\text{BS}} \frac{c_{\text{F}}}{\gamma\xi} \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa}\right)^{2/\gamma} \exp \left(-2\pi\lambda_{\text{BS}} \left(\frac{c_{\text{F}}}{2} \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa}\right)^{2/\gamma} - \frac{(c_{\text{F}} - b_{\text{F}})^3}{6a_{\text{F}}^2} \right) \right) \\
\mathcal{I}_1(\xi) &= \frac{a_{\text{K}} d_{\text{K}}^3}{3} {}_2F_1 \left(1, \frac{3}{\gamma}, 1 + \frac{3}{\gamma}, -\frac{\kappa}{\text{T}\xi} d_{\text{K}}^\gamma \right) \mathbb{1}(\xi \leq \kappa d_{\text{K}}^\gamma), \\
\mathcal{I}_2(\xi) &= \frac{b_{\text{K}} d_{\text{K}}^2}{2} {}_2F_1 \left(1, \frac{2}{\gamma}, 1 + \frac{2}{\gamma}, -\frac{\kappa}{\text{T}\xi} d_{\text{K}}^\gamma \right) \mathbb{1}(\xi \leq \kappa d_{\text{K}}^\gamma), \\
\mathcal{I}_3(\xi) &= -\frac{a_{\text{K}}}{3} \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa}\right)^{3/\gamma} {}_2F_1 \left(1, \frac{3}{\gamma}, 1 + \frac{3}{\gamma}, -\frac{1}{\text{T}} \right) \mathbb{1}(\xi \leq \kappa d_{\text{K}}^\gamma), \\
\mathcal{I}_4(\xi) &= -\frac{b_{\text{K}}}{2} \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa}\right)^{2/\gamma} {}_2F_1 \left(1, \frac{2}{\gamma}, 1 + \frac{2}{\gamma}, -\frac{1}{\text{T}} \right) \mathbb{1}(\xi \leq \kappa d_{\text{K}}^\gamma), \\
\mathcal{I}_5(\xi) &= -\frac{c_{\text{K}} d_{\text{K}}^2}{2} \left(1 - {}_2F_1 \left(1, -\frac{2}{\gamma}, 1 - \frac{2}{\gamma}, -\frac{\text{T}\xi}{\kappa} d_{\text{K}}^{-\gamma} \right) \right) \mathbb{1}(\xi \leq \kappa d_{\text{K}}^\gamma), \\
\mathcal{I}_6(\xi) &= -\frac{c_{\text{K}}}{2} \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa}\right)^{2/\gamma} \left(1 - {}_2F_1 \left(1, -\frac{2}{\gamma}, 1 - \frac{2}{\gamma}, -\text{T} \right) \right) \mathbb{1}(\xi \geq \kappa d_{\text{K}}^\gamma), \\
\mathcal{I}_7(\xi) &= \frac{c_{\text{K}}}{2} \text{R}_{\text{A}2}^2 {}_2F_1 \left(1, \frac{2}{\gamma}, 1 + \frac{2}{\gamma}, -\frac{\kappa}{\text{T}\xi} \text{R}_{\text{A}}^\gamma \right) \mathbb{1}(\xi \leq \kappa d_{\text{K}}^\gamma), \\
\mathcal{I}_8(\xi) &= -\frac{c_{\text{K}} d_{\text{K}}^2}{2} {}_2F_1 \left(1, \frac{2}{\gamma}, 1 + \frac{2}{\gamma}, -\frac{\kappa}{\text{T}\xi} d_{\text{K}}^\gamma \right) \mathbb{1}(\xi \leq \kappa d_{\text{K}}^\gamma), \\
\mathcal{I}_9(\xi) &= \frac{c_{\text{K}}}{2} \text{R}_{\text{A}2}^2 {}_2F_1 \left(1, \frac{2}{\gamma}, 1 + \frac{2}{\gamma}, -\frac{\kappa}{\text{T}\xi} \text{R}_{\text{A}}^\gamma \right) \mathbb{1}(\xi \geq \kappa d_{\text{K}}^\gamma), \\
\mathcal{I}_{10}(\xi) &= -\frac{c_{\text{K}}}{2} \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa}\right)^{2/\gamma} {}_2F_1 \left(1, \frac{2}{\gamma}, 1 + \frac{2}{\gamma}, -\frac{1}{\text{T}} \right) \mathbb{1}(\xi \geq \kappa d_{\text{K}}^\gamma), \\
\mathcal{I}_{\infty}(\xi) &= 2\pi\lambda_{\text{BS}} \sum_{k=1}^6 \mathcal{I}_k(\xi), \quad \mathcal{I}_{\text{R}_A}(\xi) = 2\pi\lambda_{\text{BS}} \left(\sum_{k=1}^4 \mathcal{I}_k(\xi) + \sum_{k=7}^{10} \mathcal{I}_k(\xi) \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Table 2. Empirical point process (ISD = Inter-Side Distance).

Point Process	Parameters
Lattice point process	ISD={100, 300}m
GPP [8] (Urban, $\beta = 0.900$)	$\lambda_{\text{BS}} = 31.56 \text{ BS/km}^2$, Area = $3.784^2 \pi \text{ km}^2$, $\gamma = 3.5$
GPP [8] (Rural, $\beta = 0.375$)	$\lambda_{\text{BS}} = 0.03056 \text{ BS/km}^2$, Area = $124.578^2 \pi \text{ km}^2$, $\gamma = 2.5$

5 Numerical Validation

In this section, some numerical results that substantiate the applicability of the IDT approach are illustrated. The parameters of the considered network deployments are summarized in Table 3. The triplets of parameters used to apply the IDT approach are obtained by solving (12).

The numerical results are reported in Fig. 1. The markers represent Monte Carlo simulations and the solid lines denote the framework in *Theorem 1*. There are three curves in the figure: i) ‘‘Empirical (R)’’ is obtained from the data sets listed in Table 3 (generated with R [10]); ii) ‘‘PPP-IDT’’ is obtained from the

Fig. 1. P_{cov} of GPP-Rural ($\beta = 0.375$) and **Fig. 2.** P_{cov} of square-lattice (ISD = 100 m and ISD = 300m).

IDT approach with the triplets of parameters obtained from (12); and iii) “PPP-H” gives the reference curve that corresponds to using homogeneous PPPs. From Fig. 1, we conclude that the IDT approach is accurate, tractable and capable of reproducing the spatial correlation of several point processes widely used in the literature.

6 Conclusion

In this paper, we have proposed a new mathematically tractable approach to model and analyze cellular networks in which the locations of the BSs are spatially correlated. The proposed approach is based on the theory of I-PPPs. The tractability and accuracy of the proposed methodology have been substantiated by using data sets available in the literature. Based on the obtained results, we conclude that IDT approach have wide applicability to the analysis and design of cellular networks. An extended version of the present paper is available in [13].

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